

Submitted on: 04.02.2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5971776

The digital collections of the university libraries in Algeria through cases studies

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Abstract:

The university libraries need the infrastructure as well as the performed skills of the librarians. The technological skills are very important in nowadays era. The observation of the websites of the libraries reveal the existence of digitization of the collection compounded of books, periodicals, theses etc. there are also digital platforms of databases through the national system of documentation access, platform of theses through the national portal of theses. Besides, the libraries express the will to develop social network. The libraries use facebook. Among them the university library of Tizi-Ouzou makes the digital collection of theses available through this vehicle.

Keywords: University Library, Digital Collection, Digital Repository, Access to Information, Digital Transformation

Introduction:

The digital collections belong to the field of library and information sciences and also can be considered as multidisciplinary in regard to the specialities concerned by the digitization. The digital preservation needs the infrastructure (Zhang; Su; Hubschman, 2021). Many means must be deployed such as the computers, servers, databases, platforms etc. The project of digitization requires also the competences of the librarians (Choi; Rasmussen, 2009), who must possess skills of librarianship and skills in the

digital environment. A long time before, Paul Otlet a great Belgian librarian has predicted the advent of the mutation concerning the documents when he stressed on the importance of information which should be sure, complete, fast and easy to obtain and diffuse (LeDeuff, 2014). The information literacy as an important vehicle of the documents and the information in general set on pillars among them the informatics, which plays a great role nowadays particularly by the development of the technology and the internet. Furthermore, the libraries must adopt the digitization as a strategic objective that should match the recommendations of the Bethesda and Berlin summit of the information society. The huge collection to digitize is a challenge for the libraries.

Problem statement: what are the functionalities of the repositories of the university libraries through their websites?

- what types of repositories?
- how do they integrate social network?

1- Technological Infrastructure:

The libraries need the infrastructure in the digitization projects (Zhang Su; Hubschman, 2021). The digital infrastructure is compounded of products made of networks, cloud services, the human operated services such as smartphones, tablets etc. It includes the machines operated devices for the use of Internet of things. The infrastructure applications can allow the use of internet of things, the artificial intelligence, software applications, the big data and blockchain and cybersecurity (Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, 2020). The architecture information is also important to catalog websites and manage the intranets (Le Deuff, 2014). The challenges deal also with the skills, which concern mainly the technology. They include imaging technologies, optical character recognition, mark-up languages, databases, web technology, interface design etc (Cho; Rasmussen, 2009). The institutional repositories are the academic materials that need the development of the infrastructure technology. The repositories can include theses, research articles of the university or a group of universities (Koutras; Bottis, 2013). The infrastructure technology has impact on the library practice digitization (Tapfuma; Hoskins, 2019).

2- Skills needed:

It is necessary to have knowledge and skills in the following areas, which are of three types:

- the skills related to technologies for research tools such as digitization, text mining, data visualization, mapping, image analysis, augmented reality and as skills of digital creation, curation, publishing etc.,
- skills related to programming which require knowledge in scripting languages, software and platforms,
- skills related to publication, teaching and communication,

- skills of library such as open access, copyright etc. (Zhang; Su; Hubschman, 2021). The skills of flexibility, enabling change and taking risks are needed (Choi; Rasmussen, 2009). At the other side, the behavioural skills are important such as independence and team work (Choi; Rasmussen, 2009). The internet searching is important and deals with the technological skills. There are skills dealing with the design and content of the websites, because it leads to the best use of the library repositories (Zimmerman; Pascha, 2009).

3- Digital collection in the practice:

We analyzed the digital collections through the websites of some universities in Algeria which showed the following:

Type of the resource	The type of access	The adress
Books	Repository	The website of the university
Theses	Portal	Pnst
Databases	National system of documentation	Sndl
Periodicals	webreview	The website of the university

Table1: websites of the libraries

The repository of the library repertoire through the website:

Title	Number	Percentage
Conferences	41	01
Memoires of master2	980	20
Monographs	95	02
Scientific publications	2295	46
Journals	05	0.10
Theses	1548	31
Total	4964	100

Table 2: repositories of the libraries

The databases repertoire in the National system of documentation:

Domain	Resources
Agriculture	
Chemistry	01
Medicine	02
Math	01
Informatics	01
Electronics	01
Telecommunications	01
Science and Technology	02
Life and Earth sciences	02
Physics	01

Materials sciences	02
Applied mathematics	01
Environment and biology	01
Economic sciences	02
Humanities and Social Sciences	02
Multidisciplinary	04

Table 3: databases of the national system of documentation

The social network repertoire through the website of the university of Oran:

- [Twitter.com/sndl.dz](https://twitter.com/sndl.dz)
- [Facebook.com/sndl.dz](https://facebook.com/sndl.dz)
- RSS feed is not working.

The university library of Tizi-Ouzou makes the theses available through the facebook, this leads to increase the use of the collections and allows feed-back of the users.

Conclusion:

The libraries need infrastructure technology and skills of the librarians. The practice showed that the library websites are rich compounded by: books, periodicals and theses digitized. The electronic resources are also very important and include many specialities. They integrate also the social network such as facebook and twitter

Acknowledgments

We adresse our acknowledgements to the libraries and librarians for the efforts made in the digital transformation.

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